

Low Dose Intravenous Dexmedetomidine is Effective in Attenuating Haemodynamic Stress Response Associated with Laryngoscopy and Intubation- Prospective Randomised Double Blinded Study

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Abstract

Background and Objective: Laryngoscopy and intubation cause an intense increase in heart rate, blood pressure and serum concentration of catecholamines leading to hypertension, tachycardia and dysrhythmias. These changes lead to advertisements in susceptible individuals. Dexmedetomidine, a novel alpha 2 agonist, has numerous applications in anaesthesia and ICU because it causes sedation, hypnosis, analgesia and sympatholytic. Hence the present study is undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of 0.5 µg/kg dexmedetomidine on haemodynamic responses to direct laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation. Also induction dose of propofol.

Methodology: 100 subjects of Age group- 18- 60 years, of either sex.; ASA grade I & II admitted for elective surgeries from various departments of McGANN Teaching District Hospital were included after obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee. The study population were randomly divided into Group D [Dexmedetomidine group] (n=50) and Group S [Saline group] (n=50) received Dexmedetomidine 0.5 µg/kg and saline respectively. SBP, DBP, MAP, Heart rate, SpO₂ were recorded at 1 min (T5), 3min (T6), 5min (T7), 10min (T8), 15 min (T9) and 30 minutes (T10) after laryngoscopy & intubation.

Results: Group D showed statistically significant fall in the hemodynamic response after laryngoscopy and intubation compared to group S; it also showed decrease in induction dose of propofol.

Conclusion: Dexmedetomidine in a dose of 0.5µg/kg body weight given over 10 minutes,10 minutes before induction significantly attenuates hemodynamic stress response to laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation without any significant side effects.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine, Hemodynamic Stress Response, Laryngoscopy and intubation, Blood Pressure, Heart Rate.

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Introduction

Endotracheal Intubation helps in establishing a definitive airway, prevents aspiration of gastric contents, and also allows for Positive pressure ventilation with higher airway pressures than facemask or an Supraglottic airway [1].

Direct laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are associated with varying degree of haemodynamic responses like tachycardia and hypertension which are variable, unpredictable and of brief duration [2]. Stress response seen during laryngoscopy and intubation are due to rise in catecholamine concentration which can cause determinental effects in coronary artery disease conditions like myocardial ischaemia and arrhythmia, hypertensive patients or intracranial neuropathology [3,4] Controlling this reflex is integral part of modern anaesthesia [5]. These changes in haemodynamics start within 5 seconds of laryngoscopy, peaks in 1- 2 minutes and returns to baseline within 5 minutes [6]. Several techniques have been used to control this stress response like limiting the duration of laryngoscopy to 15 seconds, deepening plane of anaesthesia, administration of high dose opioids, beta blockers, topical anaesthetics, alpha 2 agonists [6-8].

Nowadays, alpha 2 receptor agonist are widely used as anaesthetic adjuvant and analgesic [9] Premedication with clonidine, an α_2 -adrenergic agonist, has been recently shown to blunt the stress response to the surgical stimuli and reduce the narcotic and anesthetic requirements.

In addition, clonidine increases the cardiac baroreceptor reflex sensitivity to an increase in the blood pressure (BP) and hence stabilizes the BP. Due its mild selectivity to α_2 adrenoceptors and long half-life has limited its use [6] Dexmedetomidine is a newer α -agonist with $\alpha_2 : \alpha_1$ selectivity of

1600:1 and has gained popularity in modern anaesthesia [9]

Dexmedetomidine is a selective alpha 2 receptor agonist and an active d-isomer of medetomidine [3] Short half-life of dexmedetomidine makes it an ideal drug of IV titration [3]. It produces sedation, analgesia, sympatholysis and hypnosis without respiratory depression so, it has a wide range of application in anaesthesia and ICU [2-4]. The effects produced by dexmedetomidine is due to both central and peripheral mechanism. Most of the studies have used higher doses of dexmedetomidine (1-2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), very few studies have used low doses of dexmedetomidine (0.5-0.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) [3]

The present study is undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of a single preinduction dose of 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ dexmedetomidine on haemodynamic responses to direct laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation, and dose requirements of propofol for induction and its adverse effect in adult patients undergoing surgery under general anaesthesia.

Materials and Methods

A Prospective, Randomized, Double blinded, Placebo controlled study was conducted over a period of 8 months after obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee. The study was conducted on 100 subjects of Age group- 18- 60 years, of either sex.; ASA grade I & II; Weight 50-80 kg.; Mallampatti classes I and II undergoing elective surgeries requiring general anaesthesia. Exclusion criteria included ASA grade III and IV; Mallampatti class III and IV; Nasogastric tube insertion; Patients on sedatives, hypnotics & antidepressants; H/o cardiovascular, respiratory, hepatic, renal or endocrine diseases; Laryngoscopy time > 20 sec; Preoperative medication with clonidine and α methyl dopa; Any contraindication to

dexmedetomidine; BMI>30; Pregnant and lactating subjects.

The Sample size was calculated after detailed discussion with the statistician and was based on the observations of a pilot study conducted by Sebasteib B *et al* [18]. A sample size of 33 patients was obtained in each group by taking largest mean difference of 7.91 and standard deviation of 9.1. To clinically detect meaningful difference in heart rate and mean arterial blood pressure and considering 90% of power and 5% alpha error for the study, the minimum sample size obtained was 33 in both the groups. Assuming 10 % of non-response rate, the sample size obtained was 37. Further it was rounded off and 50 patients were taken in each group. Preoperative evaluation of the patient was done on the day before surgery. After explaining the procedure, written and informed consent was obtained and advised overnight fasting and patients were premedicated with tabl *et al* prazolam 0.5 mg the night before the surgery as our institute protocol. The study population were randomly divided into 2 groups with 50 subjects in each group by using sealed envelope technique containing the name of the group and patient was asked to choose an envelope. The envelopes will be opened by a senior anesthesiologist who is assigned to prepare the test drugs and is not involved with the study.

Group D [Dexmedetomidine group] (n=50) : received appropriate amount of I V Dexmedetomidine 0.5µg per kg body weight diluted in 20 ml of normal saline intravenously as slow infusion over 10minutes.

Group S [Saline group] (n=50): received appropriate amount of 20 ml of normal saline (0.5µg per kg body weight) over 10 minutes.

On arrival of the patients to the operating room, they were connected to a multiparameter monitor which measures the HR, SBP, DBP, MAP, EtCO₂, SpO₂ and

performs continuous ECG monitoring and the HR, SBP, DBP, MAP and SpO₂ were recorded before administering the study drug. The Cardiac rate and rhythm were also monitored by a continuous visual display of the lead II ECG. A peripheral line with an 18G IV cannula was secured and was preloaded with ringer's lactate solution at 15ml/kg. Patients received either, IV Normal Saline or IV Dexmedetomidine 0.5µg/kg 10 minutes before induction.

After completion of infusion SBP, DBP, MAP, Heart rate, SpO₂ were recorded. Prior to induction, Inj Midazolm 0.02 mg/kg, Inj Glycopyrrolate 0.004mg /kg, Inj Ondansetron 0.1 mg/kg, Pentazocine 0.5 mg /kg was administered IV. All patients were pre- Oxygenated for 3 mins with 100% oxygen, induced with Inj Propofol (1.5mg/kg) until loss of verbal contact.

After successful trial ventilation, Vecuronium 0.1 mg/kg given to facilitate laryngoscopy & intubation. SBP, DBP, MAP, Heart rate, SpO₂ will be recorded at 1 min (T₅), 3min (T₆), 5min (T₇), 10min (T₈), 15 min (T₉) and 30 minutes (T₁₀) after laryngoscopy & intubation.

During study the total dose of propofol required for induction was recorded. Surgery was commenced at the end of 10min after laryngoscopy & intubation. No form of stimulus was applied during the study period.

Side effects related to the study drug and anaesthesia were noted and attended to appropriately. A fall in MAP by 25% from the baseline was treated with adjusting inhalational agents and Inj Mephentramine 6mg IV boluses.

A fall in the HR to less than 50 b/min was treated with Inj Atropine 0.6mg IV. Any hypertension or tachycardia episodes would be treated by Inj Esmolol 10 mg IV boluses as required.

Statistical Analysis [10-12]

Data was entered into Microsoft excel data sheet and was analyzed using SPSS 22 version software.

Categorical data was represented in the form of Frequencies and Proportions. Chi-square test was used as test of significance for qualitative data. Continuous data was represented as Mean and Standard Deviation. Independent t test was used as test of significance to identify the mean difference between two quantitative variables.

Graphical representation of data: MS Excel and MS word was used to obtain Results

various types of graphs such as Bar diagram and Line diagram.

p value (Probability that the result is true) after assuming all the rules of statistical tests were considered as follows

p<0.01 – as highly statistically significant (HS)

p<0.05 – as statistically significant (S)

p>0.05 – as statistically not significant (NS)

Statistical software: MS Excel, SPSS version 22 (IBM SPSS Statistics, Somers NY, USA) was used to analyze data.

Table1: Age Distribution between two groups

		Group			
		Dexmedetomidine		Saline	
		Count	%	Count	%
AGE	<= 20 years	6	12.00%	6	12.00%
	21 - 30 Years	17	34.00%	18	36.00%
	31 - 40 Years	14	28.00%	12	24.00%
	41 - 50 Years	8	16.00%	9	18.00%
	> 50 Years	5	10.00%	5	10.00%

$\chi^2 = 0.241, df = 4, p = 0.993$ (NS)

Graph 1: Bar Diagram Showing Age Distribution between two groups

Table 2: Sex Distribution between two groups

		Group			
		Dexmedetomidine		Saline	
		Count	%	Count	%
Sex	Female	25	50.00%	32	64.00%
	Male	25	50.00%	18	36.00%

$\chi^2 = 1.999, df = 1, p = 0.157(NS)$

Graph 2: Bar Diagram Showing Sex Distribution between two groups

Table 3: Mean weight comparison between two groups

	Group	N	Mean	SD	P value
Weight	Group D	50	57.08	8.347	0.005*
	Group S	50	63.00	11.768	

Graph 3: Bar diagram showing weight comparison between two groups

Table 4: Mean Heart Rate Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

HR	Group				p value
	Dexmedetomidine		Saline		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T0	82.54	15.7	82.88	15.85	0.914(NS)
T1	73.72	15.45	84.8	17.13	0.001*(HS)
T2	73	12.24	86.84	17.82	< 0.001*(HS)
T3	74	12.03	90.32	14.5	< 0.001*(HS)
T4	74.6	11.71	87.94	14.89	< 0.001*(HS)
T5	85.16	13.06	102.8	13.42	< 0.001*(HS)
T6	84.94	13.93	101.4	12.53	< 0.001*(HS)
T7	83.44	14.21	100.52	12.03	< 0.001*(HS)
T8	81.84	18.3	97.18	14.15	< 0.001*(HS)
T9	80.24	14.95	94.66	14.49	< 0.001*(HS)
T10	79.76	14.66	90.92	15.38	< 0.001*(HS)

(P<0.01) – Highly Significant (HS), (P <0.05)- Significant (S); (P>0.05) – Not Significant (NS).
SD- standard deviation.

Graph 4: Line Diagram Showing Mean Heart Rate Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

Table 5: Mean SBP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

SBP	Group				p value
	Dexmedetomidine		Saline		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T0	127.14	12.12	127.84	13.89	0.789(NS)
T1	117.12	10.96	128.78	13.99	< 0.001*(HS)
T2	109.92	17.66	128.18	12.99	< 0.001*(HS)
T3	109.22	13.19	118.66	16.05	0.002*(HS)
T4	100.2	12.06	103.7	13.52	0.175(NS)
T5	118.92	12.94	143.22	12.58	< 0.001*(HS)
T6	111.08	13.3	127.62	13.14	< 0.001*(HS)
T7	106.52	13.2	118.68	14.76	< 0.001*(HS)
T8	102.76	14.58	114.42	14.47	< 0.001*(HS)
T9	105.74	14.73	115.08	14.15	0.002*(HS)
T10	103.72	14.51	114.96	16.44	< 0.001*(HS)

Graph 5: Line Diagram Showing Mean SBP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

Table 6: Mean DBP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

DBP	Group				p value
	Dexmedetomidine		Saline		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T0	79.72	9.5	80.9	9.99	0.547(NS)
T1	72.12	9.38	80.84	9.32	< 0.001*(HS)
T2	70.88	9.89	80.3	9.35	< 0.001*(HS)
T3	67.48	10.22	72.96	11.35	0.013*(S)
T4	61.62	10.82	63.42	11.99	0.433(NS)
T5	77.9	11.15	92.34	11.61	< 0.001*(HS)
T6	71.4	9.46	81.82	10.95	< 0.001*(HS)
T7	66.26	10.27	75.4	15.51	0.001*(HS)
T8	62.24	11.97	71.98	10.96	< 0.001*(HS)
T9	65.64	12.41	69.78	12.73	0.103(NS)
T10	61.96	12.31	69.42	15.42	0.009*(HS)

Graph 6: Line Diagram Showing Mean DBP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

Table 7: Mean MAP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

MAP	Group				p value
	Dexmedetomidine		Saline		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T0	95.53	9.36	96.55	10.61	0.611(NS)
T1	87.12	9.09	96.82	10.04	< 0.001*(HS)
T2	83.89	10.91	96.26	9.78	< 0.001*(HS)
T3	81.39	10.53	88.19	12.33	0.004*(HS)
T4	74.48	10.74	76.85	12	0.301(NS)
T5	91.57	11.28	109.3	11.16	< 0.001*(HS)
T6	84.63	10.45	97.09	11.04	< 0.001*(HS)
T7	79.68	10.82	89.83	14.15	< 0.001*(HS)
T8	75.75	12.32	86.13	11.55	< 0.001*(HS)
T9	79.01	12.96	84.88	12.14	0.021*(S)
T10	75.88	12.55	84.6	14.96	0.002*(HS)

Graph 7: Line Diagram Showing Mean MAP Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

Table 8: Mean Propofol Induction Dose Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

	Group				p value
	Dexmedetomidine		Saline		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Propofol Induction Dose	92	15.39	97.6	12.22	0.047*

Graph 8: Bar Diagram Showing Mean Propofol Induction Dose Comparison between two groups at different intervals of time

Discussion

Laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are considered as the most crucial events while

administering general anaesthesia as they provoke transient but marked sympathoadrenal response [1]. These

responses not significant in otherwise normal individuals. But in patients with cardiovascular compromise like hypertension, IHD; cerebrovascular disease and in patients with intracranial aneurysm even these transient changes can result in left ventricular failure, pulmonary edema, myocardial infarction, ventricular dysrhythmias and cerebral haemorrhage [13]. This is by far the most important indication to attenuate the hemodynamic response to laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation.

Very few studies Kumari K *et al* [3], Dey S *et al* [14], Sulaiman S *et al* [15] demonstrated that Dexmedetomidine at a dose of 0.5µg/kg was effective in the attenuation of the sympathoadrenal response to laryngoscopy and intubation, hence we decided to go ahead with a dose of 0.5 µg/kg body weight for our

present study. When rapidly infused Dexmedetomidine initially tends to stimulate the peripheral alpha-2B adrenoceptor present in the vascular smooth muscle which results in vasoconstriction and transient rise in blood pressure associated with a reflex decrease in heart rate. This untoward effect can be avoided by infusing it as slow IV over 10 minutes [16] hence we decided to infuse slowly over 10 minutes.

The distribution half-life of Dexmedetomidine, when given IV, is approximately 6 minutes [17] Kumari K *et al* [3] 2015, Dey S *et al* [14] in their studies had administered Dexmedetomidine as slow IV over 10 minutes before induction and found better hemodynamic stability. So, we decided to infuse the drug 10 min before induction as slow IV over 10 min.

Table 9: Mean HR changes following intubation in study groups compared to baseline HR

	Mean changes in HR following intubation (bpm)					
	1min	3min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
Dexmedetomidine	+ 2.62	+2.4	+0.9	-0.7	- 2.3	- 2.78
Saline	+ 19.92	+18.52	+ 17.64	+14.3	+11.78	+ 8,04

The sign (+) and (-) indicates increase and decrease in HR compared to basal HR respectively.

The HR Changes seen in our study was in concurrence with Rashmi HD *et al* [2] Sebastian *et al* [18] In Group D by about 5 min after intubation the mean heart rate reached towards baseline values and thereafter was less than baseline values throughout while in Group S the mean HR at all time intervals were on higher side of

baseline and never reached baseline values during study period.

From the above mentioned values it can be easily inferred that Dexmedetomidine is not only better in effectively blunting the tachycardic response to laryngoscopy and intubation but maintained a better profile (lowered heart rate) even after intubation and throughout the surgery.

Table 10: Mean SBP changes following intubation in study groups compared to baseline SBP

	1 min	3 min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
Dexmedetomidine	-8.22	-16.06	-20.62	-24.54	-21.4	-23.42
Saline	+15.38	-0.22	-9.16	-13.42	-12.76	-12.88

The sign (+) and (-) indicates increase and decrease in SBP compared to basal SBP respectively

Table 11: Mean DBP changes following intubation in study groups compared to baseline DBP

	Mean changes in DBP after intubation in mmhg

	1 min	3 min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
Dexmedetomidine	-1.82	-8.32	-13.46	-17.48	-14.08	-17.76
Saline	+ 11.4	+0.92	-5.9	-8.92	-11.12	-11.48

The sign (+) and (-) indicates increase and decrease in SBP compared to basal DBP respectively

Table 12: Mean MAP changes following intubation in study groups compared to baseline MAP

	Mean increase in MAP After intubation in mmhg					
	1min	3min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
Dexmedetomidine	-3.96	-10.9	-15.85	-19.78	-16.52	-19.65
Saline	+12.75	+0.54	-6.62	-10.42	-11.67	-11.95

The sign (+) and(-) indicates increase and decrease in SBP compared to basal MAP respectively

The blood pressure changes seen in our study was in concurrence with Kumari K *et al* [3] Gulabani M *et al* [7]. From above tables, Dexmedetomidine was not only able to control the Blood pressure response to laryngoscopy and intubation effectively but also lowered and further maintained the baseline blood pressure at a significantly lower level throughout study.

In our study; in the dexmedetomidine group, SBP, DBP and MAP were significantly lower than the baseline values at all intervals of the study (pre- and postinduction and up to 30 minutes post-intubation), whereas the placebo group showed significant increase in SBP, DBP and MAP at 1-minute postintubation and was near to baseline by 3min after intubation.

The maximum percentage increase in SBP, DBP and MAP at 1 min postintubation was significantly lesser in Group D compared to Group S, thereby showing that dexmedetomidine attenuated the pressor response that was observed until 5 minutes post intubation. Pressor response to tracheal incubation is due to rise in plasma catecholamine concentration maximum at 1 and persisting up to 3 minutes³ and we observed significant attenuation of this response with a lower dose of dexmedetomidine.

Conclusion

Dexmedetomidine in a dose of 0.5µg/kg body weight given slow intravenous infusion over a period of 10 minutes, 10 minutes before induction can be safely used to attenuate hemodynamic stress response to laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation without any significant side effects.

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